

BHL OpenRefine Wikidata Workflow

Sunset on the Ordos Border created during the Clark Northern China Expedition (1908 -1909) by Arthur de Carle Sowerby, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons

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This document provides a straightforward workflow to manually extract biodiversity data from the [Biodiversity Heritage Library](#) (BHL) and upload the same via [OpenRefine](#) into [Wikidata](#). It illustrates this workflow using the example of research expedition data.

Finding relevant text in BHL

The first step is to find the relevant data within BHL. One method is to search the BHL via its full text search to find appropriate content.

Screenshot of BHL. Copyright Biodiversity Heritage Library. Reused with Permission.

Alternatively locate a relevant publication within BHL, such as an annual report for a natural history institution, and search within that publication for appropriate research expedition data.

Screenshot of BHL. Copyright Biodiversity Heritage Library. Reused with Permission.

The below image - given in [the slides](#) for the *Integrating research expedition data from the Biodiversity Heritage Library into the Wikiverse* presentation at [LivingData 2025](#) - is an example of a page sourced from BHL which contains information on research expeditions.

Activities in China resulted in comprehensive biological collections received through the liberality of Dr. W. L. Abbott and Col. R. S. Clark, comprising mammals, birds, reptiles, etc., collected by Charles M. Hoy and Arthur de C. Sowerby, respectively; through the generosity of Rev. D. C. Graham, whose collections from Szechwan included many topotypes; and through the gift of the National Geographic Society from expeditions under F. R. Wulsin and under Dr. J. F. Rock. Mr. Wulsin during 1923 reached the famous Tibetan Lake Kokoran, but the collections from that locality have not yet arrived at the Museum. An interesting biological collection from Siam, made and contributed by Dr. Hugh M. Smith, is particularly important as linking up collections already in the Museum from the Malay Archipelago and Peninsula with those of the countries farther north.

United States National Museum. (1924). Report on the progress and condition of the United States National Museum (p. 5). U.S. Govt. Print. Off. Public Domain via BHL <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/34617857>

Locate or obtain a relevant data model/schema

As the intended repository for the extracted data is Wikidata, it is recommended that a compatible to Wikidata data model or schema be located or created. Wikidata has a list of schemas used for its data and relevant Wikidata WikiProjects often have lists of recommended schemas. More information on these can be found at [Wikidata:Schemas](#).

The [WikiProject Research Expeditions](#) has created a detailed [schema for research expeditions](#) and this includes a list of recommended minimum properties the group suggests be included in any Wikidata item for a research expedition. The below image shows the data model followed for this workflow.

Recommended minimum properties [[edit](#)]

property ID	property label	example expedition
P31	instance of	Q4558719
P495	country of origin	Q122705442
P17	country	Q2305
P276	location	Q122705442
P580	start time	Q2305
P582	end time	Q2328
P710	participant	Q2305
P11146	collection items at	Q1586167
P485	archives at	Q1586167

[Screenshot](#) of the WikiProject research expeditions minimum recommended properties for a research expedition item. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

Create spreadsheet

A spreadsheet should then be created (in the above example Google Sheets is used) with a column for each type of data required by the data model.

Name of expedition	instance of (P31)	Country of Origin (P495)	Country (P17)	location (P267)
Casey A. Wood's South Pacific expedition (1923)	research expedition	United States	Fiji	South Pacific
University of Iowa Fiji-New Zealand Expedition (1922)	research expedition	United States	Fiji	
William Louis Abbott Australian Expedition (1919-1922)	research expedition	United States	Australia	
Cockerell Siberia Expedition (1927)	research expedition	United States	Soviet Union	Siberia
William Louis Abbott China Expedition (1922 - 1923)	research expedition	United States	China	
Clark Northern China Expedition (1908 -1909)	research expedition	United States	China	

start time (P580)	end time (P582)	participant (P710)	collection items at (P11146)	archives at (P485)
1923	1923	Casey Albert Wood	U.S. Museum of Natural History	
May 19 1922	September 1922	Charles Cleveland Nutting	University of Iowa Museum of Natural History	University of Iowa Libraries
1919	1922	Charles McCauley Hoy	U.S. Museum of Natural History	Smithsonian Institution Archives
1927	1927	Theodore Dru Alison Cockerell	U.S. Museum of Natural History	
1922	1923	Charles McCauley Hoy	U.S. Museum of Natural History	Smithsonian Institution Archives
1908	1909	Arthur de C. Sowerby	U.S. Museum of Natural History	Smithsonian Institution Archives

Screenshots of spreadsheet by Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Referencing statements

Ideally the spreadsheet should contain either a column that provides a URL link to the source of the data or alternatively a column with the name of the scholarly article or publication that supports the statements intended to be made to Wikidata.

The former column will empower a "[reference URL](#)" reference to be added to appropriate statements uploaded to Wikidata.

The latter column can be reconciled against Wikidata in OpenRefine to obtain the Wikidata item QID for those publications. Assuming Wikidata items exist for those articles or publications, this would empower a "[stated in](#)" reference to be added to appropriate data added to Wikidata.

In some instances the URL provided by BHL for the page of text about the research expeditions can be used as the "reference URL" to support the statements to be added to Wikidata about these research expeditions.

Screenshot of BHL. Copyright Biodiversity Heritage Library. Reused with Permission.

Below is a screenshot of a Wikidata item for a publication about a research expedition. The Wikidata item for this publication can be used in "stated in" references supporting appropriate statements made on other Wikidata items.

Through Shên-kan : the account of the Clark expedition in north China, 1908-9 (Q135471039)

Item [Discussion](#)

publication about the Sowerby-Clark North China Expedition
Through Shên-kan

edit

Wikip

[In more languages](#)

[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
default for all languages	No label defined	–	
English	Through Shên-kan : the account of the Clark expedition in north China, 1908-9	publication about the Sowerby-Clark North China Expedition	Through Shên-kan
Māori	No label defined	No description defined	

Wikip

Wikip

Wikip

Wikip

Statements

instance of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> version, edition or translation edit 1 reference
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> monograph edit 1 reference
+ add value	

Wikip

Wikip

Wikip

Multil

comm

title	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Through Shên-kan : the account of the Clark expedition in north China, 1908-9 (English) edit 1 reference
+ add value	

[Screenshot](#) of an example Wikidata item for a publication dealing with a research expedition. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

organizer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Robert Sterling Clark edit 1 reference
stated in	Through Shên-kan : the account of the Clark expedition in north China, 1908-9
page(s)	2
BHL page ID	15211982

[Screenshot](#) of a statement on a research expedition item supported with a “stated in” publication reference. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

Adding data to spreadsheet

Once you have set up your spreadsheet to align with the data model add the relevant data extracted from BHL to that spreadsheet by copying and pasting the relevant text from BHL into the spreadsheet cells.

It is possible at this stage that further research will be required to locate data needed to populate the spreadsheet. For example further research may be needed to identify expedition participants or those institutions that either hold the archives or collections sourced from the expedition. Such research can be time consuming. A judgement should be made on whether this extra effort is an efficient use of time.

The act of creating Wikidata QIDs as identifiers for the research expeditions as well as adding research expedition data to Wikidata about those expeditions will facilitate and assist others to undertake further research and data enrichment.

Downloading spreadsheet and importing it into OpenRefine

Once the spreadsheet is propagated with the required data it is then imported into OpenRefine. As can be seen in the screenshot below, OpenRefine can create a project from a variety of data files.

Screenshot of OpenRefine. [Apache License 2.0](#)

Reconcile data

Once the data is imported into OpenRefine and a project has been created, it is then time to reconcile the data in that OpenRefine project against Wikidata. OpenRefine includes Wikidata reconciliation in the installation package.

As can be seen in the screenshot below it is just a matter of using the dropdown menu for each column to begin the reconciliation process.

Screenshot of OpenRefine. [Apache License 2.0](#)

Reconcile column Country of Origin (P495)

Select a service to reconcile against:

- Wikimedia Commons (en)
<https://commonsreconcile.toolforge.org/en/api>
- Wikidata reconci.link (en)
<https://wikidata.reconci.link/en/api>
- ORCID
<https://refine.codefork.com/reconcile/orcid>

Screenshot of OpenRefine. [Apache License 2.0](#)

As can be seen below further work may be needed to guide OpenRefine's reconciliation with Wikidata where there is some uncertainty as to the appropriate Wikidata item to be reconciled against.

Screenshot of OpenRefine. [Apache License 2.0](#)

The screenshot below shows an attempt to reconcile the name of the expedition to items in Wikidata. As none of these expeditions appear to exist in Wikidata OpenRefine can be asked to create a new Wikidata item at the point of when the data is being uploaded into Wikidata. Care should be taken to ensure the chance of creating duplicate Wikidata items is reduced. In this case the most common name for the expedition should be used to help increase the likelihood of reconciling against existing Wikidata items.

6 rows			Schema	Issues 1	Preview
Show as: rows records			Show: 5 10 25 50 100 500 1000 rows		
All	Name of expedition	description of expedition			
☆	1. Casey A. Wood's South Pacific expedition (1923) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match	expedition to the South Pacific in 1923			
☆	2. University of Iowa Fiji-New Zealand Expedition (1922) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match	expedition to Fiji and New Zealand in 1922			
☆	3. William Louis Abbott Australian Expedition (1919-1922) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match	expedition to Australia from 1919 to 1922 and funded by William Louis Abbott			
☆	4. Cockerell Siberia Expedition (1927) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match	expedition to Siberia in 1927			
☆	5. William Louis Abbott China Expedition (1922 - 1923) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match	expedition to China from 1922 to 1923 and funded by William Louis Abbott			
☆	6. Clark Northern China Expedition (1908 -1909) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match	expedition to northern China from 1908 to 1909			

Screenshot of OpenRefine. [Apache License 2.0](#)

The below screenshot shows how to instruct OpenRefine to create a new item for each cell after the reconciliation process has been undertaken.

6 rows Schema Issues 1 Preview

Show as: rows records Show: 5 10 25 50 100 500 1000 rows

All	Name of expedition	description of expedition	id
1.	Pacific expedition (1923)	expedition to the South Pacific in 1923	Q366
2.	New Zealand Expedition (1922)	expedition to Fiji and New Zealand in 1922	Q366
3.	Australian Expedition (1919-1922)	expedition to Australia from 1919 to 1922 and funded by William Louis Abbott	Q366
4.	Siberian Expedition (1927)	expedition to Siberia in 1927	Q366
5.	Expedition to China from 1922 to 1923 and funded by William Louis Abbott		Q366
6.	Clark Northern China Expedition		Q366

Context menu for 'Name of expedition' column:

- Facet
- Text filter
- Edit cells
- Edit column
- Transpose
- Sort...
- View
- Reconcile
 - Start reconciling...
 - Facets
 - Actions
 - Match each cell to its best candidate
 - Create a new item for each cell...
 - Create one new item for each cell in this column for all current filtered rows
 - Match all filtered cells to...
 - Discard reconciliation judgments
 - Clear reconciliation data
 - Copy reconciliation data...
 - Use values as identifiers...
 - Add column with URLs of matched entities...
 - Add entity identifiers column...

Screenshot of OpenRefine. [Apache License 2.0](#)

OpenRefine Schema

Once all the appropriate data is reconciled in the OpenRefine project the data should be placed in a schema to prepare for upload into Wikidata. The schema in OpenRefine should follow the Wikidata data model previously found or created for the project. The below screenshot shows the OpenRefine schema for a project creating new research expedition Wikidata items and uploading research expedition data to that item.

6 rows Schema Issues Preview Extensions

Target Wikibase instance: Wikidata

Start from an existing schema: Select... Save schema

Name of expedition description of expedition instance of (P31) Country of Origin (P495) Country (P17) location (P267) participant (P710) participant (P710) 2 participant (P710) 3 start time (P580) end time (P582) affiliation (P1416)
 collection items at (P11146) archives at (P485) reference url described by source on focus list of Wikimedia project (P5008) Column

Name of expedition remove

Terms

Label en Name of expedition override if present remove

Description en description of expedition override if present remove

+ add term

Statements

instance of instance of (P... remove configure add qualifier

▶ 2 references

+ add reference + add value

country of origin Country of Origin (P4... remove configure add qualifier

▶ 1 references

+ add reference + add value

country Country (P... remove configure add qualifier

▶ 1 references

+ add reference + add value

location location (P2... remove configure add qualifier

▶ 1 references

+ add reference + add value

Screenshot of OpenRefine schema for a research expedition data upload. [Apache License 2.0](#)

Issues about the schema can be seen on the Issues tab and once the schema is created it can be previewed in the Preview tab prior to upload.

6 rows Schema Issues Preview

Target Wikibase instance: Wikidata

Start from an existing schema: Select...

Screenshot of OpenRefine showing the Schema, Issues and Preview tabs. [Apache License 2.0](#)

Upload data to Wikidata

When satisfied that the OpenRefine project has been reconciled against Wikidata, that an appropriate schema has been created and that new items can be created and data can be uploaded into Wikidata, OpenRefine can then be asked to upload edits to the Wikidata Wikibase.

Screenshot of OpenRefine showing how to upload edits to the selected Wikibase. [Apache License 2.0](#)

OpenRefine will then ask the user to log into Wikidata with their username and password ensuring any edits made to Wikidata are logged as being undertaken by that user.

Wikidata account

Logging in to [Wikidata](#) lets you upload edits directly from OpenRefine.

You are encouraged to login with [bot passwords](#), see this [wiki page](#) to learn how to get one.

Username

Password

Remember me [?](#)

You can also [login with your owner-only consumer](#).

Close

Log in

Screenshot of OpenRefine showing the Wikidata login fields. [Apache License 2.0](#)

Once this step is complete, OpenRefine will create the new items and/or upload the data into Wikidata.

The screenshot shows the Wikidata page for 'Casey A. Wood's South Pacific expedition (1923)' (Q135474895). The page includes a search bar, navigation links, and a table of properties. The 'Statements' section lists several properties with their values and reference counts:

Property	Value	References
instance of	research expedition	2 references
country	Fiji	2 references
location	South Pacific Ocean	2 references
country of origin	United States	2 references

On the right side, there are links to various Wikimedia projects, all with 0 entries:

- Wikipedia (0 entries)
- Wikibooks (0 entries)
- Wikinews (0 entries)
- Wikiquote (0 entries)
- Wikisource (0 entries)
- Wikiversity (0 entries)
- Wikivoyage (0 entries)
- Wiktionary (0 entries)
- Multilingual sites (0 entries)

Screenshot of a new research expedition Wikidata item. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/)

Enrich associated Wikidata items

Once the expedition item exists it is now possible to use OpenRefine to add statements on to other Wikidata items to link to the expedition item. For example a new schema in the same OpenRefine project can be created to add “[participant in](#)” statements to participant items.

The screenshot shows the OpenRefine interface. At the top, a list of Wikidata properties is displayed, including 'participant (P710)'. Below this, a new schema named 'participant (P710)' is being created. The 'Statements' section shows a new statement being added: 'participant in' with a value of 'Name of expedit...'. The interface includes options to 'remove', 'configure', 'add qualifier', 'add reference', 'add value', and 'add statement'.

Screenshot of OpenRefine showing a new OpenRefine schema adding participant in statements to the participants of expeditions. [Apache License 2.0](https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0)

Uploading this data into Wikidata will create the following statement on the participant

Wikidata item.

Screenshot of a Wikidata item for a participant in an expedition. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

A new schema in the same OpenRefine project can also be created to add a “[main subject](#)” statement to the Wikidata item for the publication that describes the expedition. By doing so the user will be linking the publication Wikidata item to the Wikidata item for the expedition the publication discusses.

Screenshot of OpenRefine showing a new OpenRefine schema adding main subject statement to the publication about the research expedition. [Apache License 2.0](#)

See the below screenshot for an example of a publication Wikidata item that contains such a statement.

Through Shên-kan : the account of the Clark expedition in north China, 1908-9 (Q13547103)

Item [Discussion](#)

publication about the Sowerby-Clark North China Expedition
Through Shên-kan

 edit

Wik

[In more languages](#)

[Configure](#)

Wik

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
default for all languages	No label defined	–	
English	Through Shên-kan : the account of the Clark expedition in north China, 1908-9	publication about the Sowerby-Clark North China Expedition	Through Shên-kan
Māori	No label defined	No description defined	

Wik

Wik

Wik

Statements

instance of	
	1 reference
	1 reference
+ add value	

Wik

Wik

Wik

Mul

cor

title	
	1 reference
+ add value	

main subject	
	1 reference
+ add value	

Screenshot of a Wikidata item for a publication about a research expedition. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

Wikimedia Commons images

Another use of the newly created research expedition items is to facilitate the enrichment of images in Wikimedia Commons. For example, if an illustration or photograph in Wikimedia Commons depicts an expedition, this information can now be added to those images. This is done through adding structured data statements to the Wikimedia Commons files.

The below screenshots give an example of an image in Wikimedia Commons as well as the structured data statement added to that image. The structured data “[depicts](#)” statement links the Wikimedia Commons image to the Wikidata items for the subjects depicted in that image. In this case this image depicts [Hazrat Ali](#), a participant in the Clark North China Expedition, as well as the [Clark North China expedition](#) itself.

Size of this preview: [800 × 577 pixels](#). Other resolutions: [320 × 231 pixels](#) | [640 × 462 pixels](#) | [1,024 × 739 pixels](#) | [1,377 × 994 pixels](#).

[ImageMapEdit >](#)

Add a note ?

[Original file](#) (1,377 × 994 pixels, file size: 230 KB, MIME type: image/jpeg); ([request rotation](#))

[Open in Media Viewer](#)

File information

Structured data

Items portrayed in this file

[Edit](#)

depicts

from Wikidata

...

[Hazrat Ali](#)

[Mark as prominent](#)

[Clark Northern China Expedition \(1908 -1909\)](#)

[Mark as prominent](#)

Screenshot of an image and its structured data in Wikimedia Commons. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

An expedition may also be regarded as a “[significant event](#)” for an image file in Wikimedia Commons. For example, if an illustration has been uploaded to Wikimedia Commons and it depicts a type specimen collected during an expedition, the Wikidata item for that expedition could be added to the structured data for that image as a significant event related to that file.

File:Araneidae of the Clark Expedition to northern China Illustration.jpg

[File](#) [Discussion](#)

[Read](#) [Edit](#) [View history](#) [★](#) [Page](#) ▼

[Download](#) [Use this file](#) [Use this file](#) [Email a link](#) [Information](#) [✖](#)

Size of this preview: [433 x 600 pixels](#). Other resolutions: [173 x 240 pixels](#) | [346 x 480 pixels](#) | [554 x 768 pixels](#) | [739 x 1,024 pixels](#) | [1,987 x 2,753 pixels](#).

[Screenshot](#) of an illustration sourced from a scholarly article and uploaded into Wikimedia Commons. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

significant event	Edit
Clark Northern China Expedition (1908 -1909)	Mark as prominent

Screenshot of structured data statement attached to the above image sourced from a publication describing new species of spider collected during the [Clark Northern China Expedition](#). Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

Taxa Wikidata items

Taxa Wikidata items can also be enriched by linking those items to research expedition items, where appropriate. For example “[Named after](#)” statements can be added if the taxon has been named in honour of an expedition or an expedition participant. The research expedition might also be regarded as a “[significant event](#)” for a taxon if the tye specimen was collected during a particular expedition.

Chathamidia expeditionis (Q125386237)

named after	Chatham Islands Expedition 1954
	↳ 0 references
significant event	Chatham Islands Expedition 1954
	↳ 0 references

[Screenshot of statements added to a taxon Wikidata item](#). Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

Conclusion

By creating or enriching research expedition Wikidata items and undertaking linking of such items in and via Wikidata, editors can assist with efforts to provide standardized data about research expeditions, help with the creation and empower the reuse of identifiers for research expeditions, and assist with the creation of rich connections to and between expedition participants, locations, institutions, and related collections, publications and archives.

These efforts improve the discoverability and accessibility of research expedition data and also helps to provide context to that data, for both researchers and institutions reusing the same.

Helpful links

[Wikidata WikiProject Research Expeditions](#)

[TDWG modelling research expeditions working group](#)

[Wikidata:Basic Editing via OpenRefine](#)

[List of OpenRefine tutorials and resources](#)

[Structured data on commons](#)

Further reading

von Mering S, Cubey RWN, Endresen D, Hendriksen A, Leachman S, Mietchen D, Santos J (2024) *Advancing Community Curation of Research Expeditions: A Collaborative Journey with Wikidata and Biodiversity Information Standards*. Biodiversity Information Science and Standards 8: e138921. <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.8.138921>

Leachman S, Schrader L (2024) *Delving Into Te Papa Research Expedition Data*.
Biodiversity Information Science and Standards 8: e135809.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.8.135809>